

Trinuclear complexes of alkali metals with anhydrous nickel salicylate and copper salicylate

Sheo Satya Prakash^a, Deepa Bariar^a, J. Kumar^a, Manilal^a, Syed Khalid Mustafa^b and Nilima Dhar^c

^aP.G. Department of Chemistry, A. N. College, Patna-800 013, Bihar, India

^bOriental College, Patna City, Bihar, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, J. D. Women's College, Patna, Bihar, India

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Abstract : Ni(HSal)₂ and Cu(HSal)₂ complexes have been used as ligands in the synthesis of trinuclear alkali metal complexes having general formula [Ma(HL)₂.2MbL], where Ma = Cu^{II} or Ni^{II}; HL = salicylic acid, Mb = Li⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺; L = α -nitroso- β -naphthol (1N2N), 8-hydroxyquinoline (8HQ), NaSCN and KBr. These trinuclear complexes are considerably less soluble in ethanol than the complex ligand. Magnetic spectral and infrared spectral data suggest that they are oxygen bridged trinuclear complexes.

Keywords : Nickel salicylate, copper salicylate, alkali metal complexes.

Introduction

A lot of work has been reported with metal complexes as ligands¹. It has been observed that transition metal complexes as ligands, combine with metal ions forming stable compounds. Using Ni(HSal)₂ and Cu(HSal)₂ as metal complex ligands, we describe here synthesis of a few oxygen bridged trinuclear complexes of alkali metal ions. Ni(HSal)₂ and Cu(HSal)₂ act as bidentate ligands, coordination being through the carboxylate oxygen and the phenolic -OH group².

Results and discussion

Analytical data suggest the general formula [Ma(HL)₂.2MbL], where Ma = Cu^{II} or Ni^{II}; HL = salicylic acid; Mb = Li⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺ and L = α -nitroso- β -naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline, NaSCN and KBr.

The colours of the adducts are different from those of the metal complex ligands. The higher decomposition temperatures of these adducts compared to metal complex ligands, indicated strong bonding between oxygen atom of metal complex ligands and the alkali metal ions. The adducts were stable under dry condition. The colour, decomposition temperatures and other properties of the adducts are given in Table 1.

The magnetic moment value of 3.26 B.M. for nickel

salicylate is higher than the spin only value (2.83 B.M.) which suggests some orbital contribution to the magnetic moment. These higher magnetic moments may be due to change in geometry from octahedral to tetrahedral. The magnetic moments of copper salicylate and its adducts lie in the normal range of magnetic moment of copper(II) complexes which suggests that there is no metal-metal interaction.

The infrared spectra of anhydrous nickel salicylate and anhydrous copper salicylate are very similar to nickel salicylate tetrahydrate³. This may be due to the change in the extent of hydrogen bonding after removal of water of crystallisation. It suggests that structures of complex ligands are similar to that of nickel salicylate tetrahydrate.

The spectra of the adducts are very much similar to the spectra of complex ligands. The symmetric stretching frequency and the antisymmetric stretching frequency of the COO⁻ group in the spectra of adducts have been observed in 1410-1420 and 1535-1590 cm⁻¹ range respectively. The rise of symmetric stretching frequency of COO⁻ group from the value in the free ion (1387 cm⁻¹) and bands in the 1535-1590 cm⁻¹ range which is the range of bridging COO⁻ group. Suggests that COO⁻ group is still a bridging group in the adducts. In complex ligands, the COO⁻ group bridges in between two transition metals

Table 1

Compds.	Colour	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		Magnetic moment	Selected IR bands (cm ⁻¹)	
			Ni/Cu	N		Asym COO	MOH/COH
Ni(HSal) ₂ = L	Green	Above 300			3.26	1568	1335
L.(Na1N2N) ₂	Brown	Above 300	8.8 (8.9)	4.2 (4.0)	3.56	1575	1327
L.(Li8HQ) ₂	Brown	> 300	8.8 (9.0)	4.0 (4.2)	3.80	1570	1325
L.(KBr) ₂	Greenish	> 300	9.2 (10.0)	-	3.80	1568	1330
L.(NaSCN) ₂	Brown	> 300	9.2 (9.8)	4.1 (4.5)	3.80	1585	1333
Cu(HSal) ₂ = L'	Greenish blue	275	-	-	1.94	1590	1335
L'.(Na1N2N) ₂	Yellow green	Above 300	8.75 (8.0)	-	2.00	1580	1325
L'.(Li8HQ) ₂	Yellow	> 300	9.2 (10.0)	-	2.20	1595	1325
L'.(KBr) ₂	Yellow brown	> 300	9.5 (10.3)	-	2.10	1572	1330
L'.(NaSCN) ₂	Brown	> 300	9.8 (10.7)	4.2 (4.8)	2.20	1585	1332

(Cu/Ni) where as in the adducts it most probably bridges a transition metal to an alkali metal.

Another characteristics feature of the spectra of the complex ligands and the adducts in the lowering of the phenolic -OH bending vibration mode. There is a successive decrease in the phenolic -OH bending vibration as we go along the series of sodium salicylate complex ligand adducts. This vibration for sodium salicylate has been reported at 1340 cm⁻¹⁴, while for complex ligand (nickel salicylate) with occurs at 1335 cm⁻¹. A decrease of 5 cm⁻¹ suggests that phenolic -OH is coordinated in the complex ligands. The phenolic -OH bending vibrations in the spectra of adducts occur in range 1333-1320 cm⁻¹. So, a further decrease of 2-15 cm⁻¹ in the phenolic -OH bending vibrations in the adducts, suggests that phenolic -OH is further coordinated in the adducts most probably to alkali metals.

The visible absorption spectrum of anhydrous nickel salicylate shows typical octahedral absorption bands at 350, 675 and 1000 nm. The electronic spectra of alkali metal adducts is different in nature; observed near by 600 nm and 1200 nm. The change in the spectra of anhydrous nickel salicylate upon complexation indicates that

the structure of adducts is different from that of the complex ligand. So, a tetrahedral structure is expected for the adducts.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The method of synthesis was to treat anhydrous nickel salicylate with alkali metal salts in 1 : 2 in chloroform to which a few drops of absolute ethanol have been added. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate with magnetic stirrer for 3-4 h, when the content went into solution and the adducts precipitated from hot solutions. They were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol/chloroform and dried at 80 °C. Adducts were finally kept in a desiccator over solid anhydrous CaCl₂.

Nickel was estimated by gravimetric method and copper was estimated volumetrically. The IR spectra of the ligand and adducts were made in nujol. The electronic spectra were recorded on a Cary-14 spectrophotometer and magnetic moments were measured by Gouy method.

On the basis of above mentioned facts, the following structure has been proposed for the adducts.

where Ma = Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}; Mb = Na or Li or K; HL = α -nitroso- β -naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline, KBr, NaSCN.

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